

Information Sheet

Purpose of the Study. I am Dr Catherine Ferris, [IReL](#) Open Scholarship Officer (Maynooth University) and Project Manager of the National Open Access Monitor Project, funded by the National Open Research Forum.

This project will develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access. The key objectives and expected outcomes are to:

- Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level
- Build on previous NORF work, engaging with national stakeholders (DFHERIS, NORF, NORF 2022 Open Research Fund projects, HEA, research funding organisation, research performing organisations, national research infrastructures, publishers etc.) to gather and validate user requirements for Open Access monitoring
- Work with external vendors to deliver reports and a national dashboard to help Ireland publish, analyse and track open access rates at the national level.
- Document challenges that should be addressed in long-term monitoring solutions and recommend steps to be taken, including workflows for data validation and enrichment.
- Work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard in line with international best practice through stakeholder collaboration with institutions, funders etc. and direct input or validation where possible.
- Following NORF and Science Europe recommendations, ensure that the monitor uses data and bibliographic databases that are openly accessible, is built using open infrastructure, and is publicly accessible to view and analyse.

A copy of the Project Plan is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331432>

What will the study involve? The project will be carried out over a two-year period (1 November 2022 – 1 November 2024) and contributions will be invited throughout this period. Advisory Group contributions will be collected in meetings and by email.

Who has approved this study? This study has been reviewed and received ethical approval from Maynooth University Research Ethics committee. You may have a copy of this approval if you request it.

Why have you been asked to take part? You have been asked due for your expertise as a member of the NORF National Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief Group.

Do you have to take part?

No, you are under no obligation whatsoever to take part in this research. It is entirely up to you to decide whether or not you would like to take part. If you decide to do so, you will be asked to sign a consent form and given a copy and the information sheet for your own records. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and/or to withdraw your information up until such time as the contributions are actioned upon for the development of the NORF National OA Monitor. This will happen throughout the project and all participants will be informed of the relevant dates in advance. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your relationship with Maynooth University.

What information will be collected? This group will hold an advisory role for IReL and the Project Manager, complimenting the governance role of Maynooth University and the obligations set out by NORF. It will provide expert guidance when required throughout the project, e.g. by contributing to tender reviews; validating the pilot results against NORF requirements; and contributing to the recommendation of which solution NORF should proceed with.

All contributor organisations will also be asked to monitor and track the costs associated with contributing to this project. This data will be provided in the final report to the funder, in an anonymised format (to the high-level stakeholder group) to demonstrate the cost of this work to the national research system.

Will your participation in the study be kept confidential? No, transparency is a core principle of this project. Therefore, it is a project aim to capture contributor provenance at the outset: to capture *who/which entity* contributes *what* to the National Open Access Monitor Project. This will enable all decisions made in the delivery of the Monitor to be transparent. Identities of the NORF National OA Monitor Advisory Group will be published.

This form is to obtain explicit consent to identify you, to attribute your contribution to you, and to include your name, job title, organisation and ORCID iD (if provided) within the project documentation which will be used for the delivery of the National Open Access Monitor and archived under a Creative Commons license on Zenodo.

All electronic information will be encrypted and held securely on MU servers. It must be recognised that, in some circumstances, confidentiality of research data and records may be overridden by courts in the event of litigation or in the course of investigation by lawful authority. In such circumstances the University will take all reasonable steps within law to ensure that confidentiality is maintained to the greatest possible extent.

What will happen to the information which you give?

- Confidential procurement and tender data will be restricted to IReL Executive, MU Finance and Procurement Offices, and the members of the tender reviewing committee (including the Advisory Group). This data will not be archived in Zenodo.
- The public tender announcement will be published and archived in Zenodo
- Advisory Group decisions (e.g. recommendations, actions) will be archived in Zenodo.
- Your emails and email addresses will not be included in the project documentation or archived in Zenodo.

During the research process, data will be stored in Microsoft OneDrive, under the MU institutional subscription. Data will regularly be archived under a Creative Commons license in Zenodo for preservation and public sharing purposes and will be preserved for the lifetime of the repository. In case of closure of Zenodo, the repository states “best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.”

What will happen to the results? The Advisory Group contributions will inform and shape the National Open Access Monitor. Research outputs in many formats (reports, presentations etc) will be produced to document the progression and deliverables of the project. The contributions will be archived, with the project documentation, under a Creative Commons license on Zenodo, to meet the transparency goals of the project. A copy of the research findings will be made available to you upon request.

What are the possible disadvantages of taking part? A possible disadvantage to you is the time it takes to contribute, under the required deadlines to deliver the project.

Any further queries? If you need any further information, you can contact me: Dr Catherine Ferris, catherine.ferris@mu.ie

If you agree to take part in the study, please complete and sign the consent form overleaf and return to catherine.ferris@mu.ie

Thank you for taking the time to read this

Consent Form

I.....agree to contribute to the National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group, project managed by Dr Catherine Ferris.

Please tick each statement below:

The purpose and nature of the study has been explained to me in writing. I've been able to ask questions, which were answered satisfactorily.

I am participating voluntarily.

I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether that is before it starts or while I am participating.

I understand that I can withdraw permission to use the data right up to when it will be actioned upon for the development of the National Open Access Monitor, and that I will be informed of such relevant dates in advance

It has been explained to me how my data will be managed and that I may access it on request.

I understand the limits of confidentiality as described in the information sheet

I agree for my data, attributed to me, to be retained indefinitely in the Zenodo archive and to be made available for reuse under an open Creative Commons license, as described in the information sheet

Signed.....

Date.....

Participant Name in block capitals

I the undersigned have taken the time to fully explain to the above participant the nature and purpose of this study in a manner that they could understand. I have explained the risks involved as well as the possible benefits. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them.

Signed.....

Date.....

Researcher Name in block capitals: CATHERINE FERRIS

If during your participation in this study you feel the information and guidelines that you were given have been neglected or disregarded in any way, or if you are unhappy about the process, please contact the Secretary of the Maynooth University Ethics Committee at research.ethics@mu.ie or +353 (0)1 708 6019. Please be assured that your concerns will be dealt with in a sensitive manner.

For your information the Data Controller for this research project is Maynooth University, Maynooth, Co. Kildare. Maynooth University Data Protection officer is Ann McKeon in Humanity house, room 17, who can be contacted at dataprotection@mu.ie. Maynooth University Data Privacy policies can be found at <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/data-protection>.

Two copies to be made: 1 for participant, 1 for PI